

Awareness of the Benefits of Strategic Planning For Educational Institutions

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to determine the benefits of strategic planning for Islamic educational institutions. The method used is a literature review, by collecting various supporting article references from national journals. The results of this study explain, if strategic planning can be made and implemented correctly and supported by leadership commitment, then strategic planning can provide benefits for Islamic educational institutions, including: (1) Strategic planning can strengthen the "critical mass" into a team that compact, because it is directed to adhere to basic values, main systems and common goals, (2) Strategic planning can help to optimize the performance of Islamic educational institutions, (3) Strategic planning can help leaders to always focus attention and adhere to a framework for overall improvement efforts continuous, (4) Strategic planning provides guidelines for daily decision making, and (5) Strategic planning always makes it easy to measure the organization's progress in achieving its goals of improving quality and productivity. The benefits of educational strategic planning are things that need to be considered to create quality Islamic educationh.

INTRODUCTION

In Chapter II of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, regarding the Foundations, Functions and Objectives of Education, it is emphasized that national education functions to develop abilities and form a dignified national character and civilization in order to educate the nation's life, aiming to developing the potential of students to become human beings who believe and are devoted to God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens. (Sari, 2020).

To realize these national education goals, of course it is not as easy as turning the palm of your hand, but various optimal efforts are needed. Among the most strategic efforts is that every educational institution is willing and able to prepare and have a measurable and targeted plan. In Indonesia, there are several regulations governing planning, both for government agencies and private institutions. There are three commonly known planning terms, namely long-term planning of 25 years called RIP (Master Development Plan), medium-term planning of 5 years called Strategic Plan (Renstra), and short-term planning of 1 year called Annual Work Plan (RKT). which includes all matters related to education, such as vision, mission, goals, objectives, strategic and technical work programs which are generally intended to meet and exceed national education standards.

Based on Government Regulation Number 19 of 2005 concerning National Education Standards, the implementation of education is said to be of quality if it is carried out in accordance with predetermined national education standards (National Education Standards, 2021). In this case there are eight education standards, namely: (1) content standards, (2) process standards, (3) graduate competency standards, (4) standards for educators and education personnel, (5) facilities and infrastructure standards, (6) standards management, (7) financing standards, and (8) education assessment standards. These eight standards are

interrelated to support the implementation of a quality learning process. Thus, it can be said that the quality of education lies in the quality and quality of learning and can provide changes in management.

Islamic Religious Education is one component of education which aims to instill religious values in students so that they become people of faith and piety as is the goal of national education. The aim of Islamic Religious Education is the formation of changes in attitudes and behavior in accordance with the instructions of Islamic religious teachings (Hasim, et al, 2021). As was done by the Prophet Muhammad SAW in an effort to convey the call of religious teachings by preaching, conveying teachings, giving examples, training acting skills, providing motivation and creating a social environment that supports the implementation of the idea of forming a Muslim personality. For this reason, efforts, activities, methods, tools and an environment that support its success are needed.

Apart from that, Islamic education is not just a process of trying to transfer knowledge or religious norms, but also trying to create physical and spiritual manifestations in students so that in the future they will become a generation that has noble character, character and personality, a complete Muslim personality.

One strategy in achieving an increase in the quality of Islamic education is to form an Islamic educational organization (Islamic educational institution) that has potential, has advantages that can create and offer more customer value, and has better performance. To achieve this, of course Islamic educational institutions must be supported by planning that can improve the quality of their institutions effectively and efficiently. Planning has an important role in Islamic educational institutions. With planning, it will be possible to predict future work, and will even be able to predict the possible results that will be achieved.

Educational institutions (including Islamic educational institutions at all levels) as formal institutions are required to have clear and measurable plans. An educational plan is an important foundation throughout the educational process. Educational planning can clarify the direction and objectives of educational implementation, as well as enable the management of educational institutions to be carried out more effectively and efficiently. Among the steps in educational planning, namely strategic planning (renstra), coordinative (managerial) planning and educational operational planning. Strategic planning involves determining the policies taken in matters of education, the approaches used, and the goals and objectives to be achieved. is a combination of concepts and art in formulating, implementing and evaluating to achieve organizational goals (Ulfa et al., 2019).

Strategic planning (Renstra) is an important component in the management of an organization because it provides guidance and guidance in providing services to the community and stakeholders. The plan is prepared and implemented by managers/managers to achieve broader organizational goals. For this reason, in its application within an organization, organizational leaders need to create a strategic plan that will be coordinated with all work partners to be carried out together to achieve the desired goals of an organization. Therefore, the process of preparing the Strategic Plan must involve all stakeholders. The characteristics of a good strategic plan are: integrated, multi-year, updated, participatory and its implementation can be monitored.

There is a phenomenon that indicates that some Islamic educational institutions are not yet of high quality because some of the stakeholders are not yet able to prepare strategic plans, some are capable but not yet serious and even still consider it a mere formality, some are full of awareness but there are also those who join in. , there are also those who still don't understand it. Thus, this article will explain the importance of awareness of the benefits of strategic planning for Islamic educational institutions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Planning

Planning as an activity to determine long-term development plans.

Johnson Kast Rozens-Weig in (Munthe, 2021) defines strategic planning as the process of determining main targets, policies that regulate the procurement and utilization of resources and strategies that regulate the procurement and utilization of resources to achieve goals. Meanwhile (Kaufman, 2019) states that strategic planning is a process carried out by formulating policies that determine changes in the character or direction of an organization. (Kaufman, 2019) provides a definition of strategic planning for educational institutions, namely planning that begins by identifying what should be and what can be done, then works to ensure that all parts of the educational institution's organization can be designed appropriately.

From the opinions of the experts above, a conclusion can be drawn that strategic planning is the process of deciding what program an organization will carry out, by identifying what should and what can be done. A guide for the organization from the conditions currently being faced to the conditions in the next few years (future) in order to achieve maximum goals and in accordance with what is desired.

METHODS

It can also be interpreted as Strategic The method used is a literature review by collecting various supporting articles consisting of national journals. The articles reviewed are related to the topic of the importance of strategic planning in improving the quality of education which begins with searching for and collecting articles that are relevant to the article being written. The search and collection of articles came from Google School starting from May to June 2023 using the keyword "Benefits and urgency of Strategic Planning".

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Study Result

The results of the literature study of various relevant articles regarding the importance of strategic planning in improving the quality of Islamic educational institutions are analyzed in table 1 below:

Table 1. Results of Literature Review

No	Supporting Articles	Findings	Reflection
1	Islamic Education Development Planning Strategy in Indonesia (Muhamad Nuryasin, et al., 2019)	Until now, aspects of educational planning in the Islamic education environment, both macro and micro, are still seen as unimportant. Educational planning, which should be an integral part of the management of Islamic education, is often neglected and has not become a tradition in the development of Islamic education.	Islamic Education Planning Strategy, along with various possibilities and alternatives that might be implemented in developing Islamic education in the future. Offers several alternative Islamic education planning models, especially those related to the dynamics of the community who are education stakeholders. Planning must have the aim of understanding; concepts, paradigms, strategies and planning steps for Islamic education. Planning can formulate goals to be achieved and controlled to be carried out effectively and efficiently. Selection of the right program, to achieve goals and identification and mobilization of resources which are always limited.
2	Urgency of Planning Strategic and Management Resource – Madrasa Man Era Industrial Revolution 4.0 (Moch. Charis Hidayat and Aldo Redho Syam, 2020)	This paper examines studies regarding the urgency of strategic planning and human resource management in madrasas. This paper is the result of a literature review with data obtained from document study activities, both from reference books and international and national journals. This study proposes findings that the urgency of strategic planning and human resource management in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 in madrasas today is essentially to avoid disaster or failure of	One of the management functions that must be managed well is strategic planning, namely planning that is able to predict the life, resilience and progress of the madrasah in the future by improving its functions. in resource management human power must implemented optimally, by focusing on achieving madrasah goals which has been determined and implement it in programs and activities, which then develop, including collecting data to evaluate the effectiveness of educational process programs. Educational planning provides clarity of direction in the business process implementation of education, so that the management of the institution education will be available implemented more effectively

		<p>madrasas, madrasa managers are expected to be able to manage their madrasas in accordance with the basic needs and management systems required by each stage of the cycle. his life</p>	<p>and efficient.</p>
3	<p>The Urgency of Islamic Education Planning Post the Covid-19 Pandemic (Akhmad, 2021)</p>	<p>The aim of this research is to explain the urgency of planning Islamic education after COVID19</p>	<p>The results of this research are that planning Islamic education in Distance Learning Learning From Home Online (PJJ BDR Online) due to COVID-19, starts with student readiness, preparing an Online Learning Implementation Plan (RPPD), using strategies in learning, using learning media, learning methods, learning resources and teaching materials, time allocation, and assessment of formative learning outcomes.</p>
4	<p>The Urgency of Strategic Planning in Improving Education Development and Quality (Rika Maria and Hardiyanto, 2021)</p>	<p>The preparation of a Strategic Plan is a reference in operationalizing activity plans with their main tasks and functions. Strategic plans are not merely prepared and left in silence, but the strategic plans that have been made must be implemented as a reference in an organization so that it can work effectively and achieve the desired/appropriate results. targeted. This research was conducted at MTsN 10 Tanah Datar, West Sumatra, aiming to illustrate the importance of strategic planning in improving the development and quality of education.</p>	<p>The benefits of strategic planning carried out by the Madrasah, are effectively systematic and programmed, so that it can improve the development and quality of education at MTsN 10 Tanah Datar, including increasing the various achievements achieved by MTsN 10 Tanah Datar, such as being ranked best 1 in the performance assessment of the Head of Madrasah Level Sumatra West, the increasing number of students registering at MTsN 10 Tanah Datar and also other achievements such as becoming an adiwiyata madrasa, a research madrasa and a child-friendly madrasa.</p>
5	<p>EDUCATION-BASED Educational Strategic Planning Religion, Philosophy, Psychology, and Sociology (Arbainsyah, et al., 2022)</p>	<p>This research describes and analyzes the what, why, and how of strategic planning for education based on religion, philosophy, psychology, and sociology.</p>	<p>Educational strategic planning is a plan for achieving 5 or 7 year goals of systematic learning which is: (1) religiously based, meaning inspired by the belief in God's teachings which commands careful planning, by means of preparing and investing potential resources, adapting abilities, oriented towards winning the struggle and general welfare, savings, and determining output and outcomes; (2) philosophy-based means inspired by academic knowledge about the nation's cultural values, with a view of godliness, humanity, unity, democracy and social justice; (3) psychology-based, meaning inspired by the science of mind and behavior, especially the development of human cognition, through the stages of knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation; and (4) sociologically based, meaning inspired by social</p>

			science about symbolic interactions, through the stages of interpreting symbols, acting and interacting differently, modifying meanings, choosing meanings, determining actions and different groups.
6	The Concept of Strategic Planning in Educational Institutions (Muh. Yusril, et al, 2022)	Describe the concept of strategic planning in educational institutions	Strategic planning is planning that is linked to an approach to: a) formulating a vision and mission, b) identifying <i>goals</i> that guide the mission, c) determining targets to help achieve goals, and d) creating work plans (Renstra) that encourage achieving targets. Apart from that, strategic planning can be carried out using <i>SWOT analysis</i> in measuring or evaluating activities in organizational/school units by evaluating <i>Strengths</i> , <i>Weaknesses</i> , <i>OPPORTUNITIES</i> (opportunities) and <i>Threats</i> . There are several things and input that the researcher wants to convey based on the conclusion, that: 1) the school principal in designing an activity needs to be considered as carefully as possible because the decisions taken affect the future, 2) each <i>stakeholder can use SWOT analysis</i> to design a plan that mature, because <i>SWOT analysis</i> can identify opportunities and even weaknesses in an activity. 3) in this research, the researcher considers there is a lack of references and future researchers can maximize these references.

Source : Processed Data, 2023

The results of the literature review in table 1 show that there is the importance of awareness of the benefits of strategic planning for Islamic educational institutions. Efforts to improve the quality of education are a strategic point in efforts to create quality education. The benefits of planning in providing education provide clarity of direction for each activity, so that each activity can be attempted and implemented as efficiently and effectively as possible to maintain the quality of Islamic educational institutions. In this case, in order to improve the quality of Islamic education, it is necessary to develop national education standards, in this case content standards and process standards in education. Apart from presenting the urgency of educational management and strategies as important things that must be fulfilled in order to create quality education, review articles have also presented strategic planning steps for educational management (Djamil, 2021).

Strategic management is seen as an evolution of management for two reasons, namely (1) strategy is an organization's big plan to overcome current challenges and simultaneously achieve the organization's vision and mission in the future, (2) organizations implement strategic management in response to changes in the world in improving competitiveness for future success. (Naution, 2018)

Strategic planning is planning that is linked to an approach to: a) formulating a vision and mission, b) identifying goals that guide the mission, c) determining targets to help achieve goals, and d) creating work plans (Renstra) that encourage achieving targets. In addition, strategic planning can be carried out using SWOT analysis in measuring or evaluating activities in organizational units by evaluating strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. Each stakeholder can use SWOT analysis to design a thorough plan, because SWOT analysis can identify both the internal and external environment of Islamic educational institutions.

The organizational environment is an important factor in preparing strategic plans for Islamic educational institutions. Strategic planning generally includes three steps: strategy formulation, strategy implementation, and strategy evaluation. Strategic development includes formulating a vision and mission,

identifying opportunities and threats outside the organization, identifying the organization's internal strengths and weaknesses, setting long-term goals, developing alternative strategies, and selecting specific strategies for implementation.

The factors that form the basis for planning Islamic educational institutions and determining organizational goals, the first is the climate or environment within the organization, and the second is the external environment. Reiterating this, in connection with the brief description above, it can be concluded that climate and environment are key components of organizational planning and setting organizational goals. Therefore, organizational improvement requires all relevant information about internal and external conditions (Sari & Sudirman, 2019).

Strategic planning is an alternative that should be a way out of the problems surrounding the world of Islamic education in Indonesia today. All organizations (educational institutions) face two types of "environment": internal environment and external environment. The larger the organization, the more complex the forms, types, and nature of interactions involved in dealing with these two types of "environment." One of the consequences of this complexity is that the decision-making process becomes more difficult and complex (Iskandar, 2017). The great advantage of strategic planning is that it offers organizations the opportunity to empower individuals. Empowerment is the act of encouraging, rewarding, training initiative and imagination in decision making to increase understanding of effectiveness.

DISCUSSION

Based on the review of the national journal articles mentioned above, it can be explained that the implementation of education is very dependent on good management, including planning, organizing, directing and controlling (Syoviana, 2021). Management strategy is the process of preparing, implementing and reviewing process steps to achieve organizational goals in the future, so strategy involves the participation of all components of the organization and determining strategies to be implemented and executed (Budio, 2019).

One of the management functions that must be managed well is strategic planning, namely planning that is able to predict the future life, resilience and progress of an organization by improving human resource management work which must be carried out optimally, with a focus on achieving predetermined organizational goals. Develop programs and activities to implement this goal, including collecting data to evaluate program effectiveness (Hidayat & Syam, 2020).

Creating a strategic plan will help in carrying out activity plans with main tasks and functions. Strategic plans are not only prepared and created, but must be implemented as a reference in carrying out tasks within the organization so that it can function effectively and achieve the expected results (Maria & Hadiyanto, 2021). Furthermore, the application of strategic control in the implementation of the education system allows educational institutions (including Islamic schools and the world of Islamic education) to be more active in shaping the future of education in today's global world.

If implemented correctly and supported by leadership commitment, strategic planning can provide benefits for Islamic educational institutions as follows:

1. Strategic planning can strengthen the "critical mass" into a cohesive team, because it is directed at adhering to core values, main systems and common goals. Critical mass is a group of core personnel of an organization who have the motivation, talent (aptitude) and fundamental knowledge (profound knowledge) to improve the quality and productivity of Islamic educational institutions.

2. Strategic planning can help to optimize the performance of Islamic educational institutions. Organizational performance increases if all functions or parts of an educational institution work together harmoniously. If members of educational institutions from various departments work together in a process that crosses functional lines, it is very likely that system optimization in the organization can be achieved. In this connection, a critical mass is needed who understands the system and understands how its activities can contribute to the educational institution system as a whole. In this way sub-optimization can be avoided. Sub-optimization occurs when each member tries to maximize the achievement of their respective goals. This can ultimately be detrimental to achieving the total goals of the organization. Systems thinking is an important component in strategic planning and total quality management (TQM). Systems thinking is the ability to combine parts into a totality. Efforts to improve process interactions are also a major component of systems

thinking. Without strategic planning based on systemic thinking, the sub-optimization that occurs is considered as if it were the right thing. Strategic planning that is carried out correctly can help an organization to identify situations that can lead to sub-optimization. To avoid sub-optimization, leaders can carry out cross-functional process management and lead their members to work coordinatively.

3.Strategic planning can help leaders always focus attention and adhere to a framework for continuous improvement efforts. Strategic planning always helps leaders focus attention so that planned improvements and innovations can be evaluated to what extent these activities support the vision for Islamic educational institutions. Furthermore, strategic planning can also provide a framework for prioritizing, organizing and integrating improvement efforts. Translating strategic objectives into reality requires each function within an Islamic educational institution to determine product and service processes that will support the achievement of these objectives. Efforts to meet the needs of key "customers" often involve joint efforts from various functions or sections within the organization. The managers/managers of these sections must work together so that the improvement plans for each section have a total effect on the optimal "performance" of Islamic educational institutions. This requires that strategic objectives need to be supported by a broad strategy. Furthermore, supporting activity plans must also be developed for each strategy. Then the focus and framework as mentioned above are also useful when leaders and managers hold discussions about resource allocation.

4.Strategic planning provides guidance for daily decision making. Strategic planning not only guides large businesses, but also guides daily activities. Strategic planning is expected to influence all levels in the organization, by clearly communicating strategic objectives at all levels. Communicating strategic goals clearly allows each member to make decisions in line with efforts to achieve organizational goals. Thus, organizational goals can be achieved through mobilizing and directing the daily activities of all members of educational institutions.

5.Strategic planning always makes it easy to measure an organization's progress in achieving its goals of improving quality and productivity.

The main elements of TQM are the existence of process goals to achieve these goals and measurements to assess process progress. Management of quality Islamic educational institutions provides the best service to the community through the management of quality Islamic educational institutions which can produce quality generations and proper management of institutions which can bring positive change to the country (Nahrowi, 2021).

Islamic educational institutions are expected to be able to apply the concept of strategic thinking and behavior to initiate and influence various demands, routine and bureaucratic activities, but more than that, Islamic educational institutions can be strategic in achieving the expected goals. Where it is hoped that all components of educational institutions need to work together by creating synergy and good coordination in order to achieve maximum goals. Strategic planning in improving education is an important need that must be fulfilled. Awareness of the benefits of educational strategic planning is something that needs to be considered to create quality Islamic education.

CONCLUSION

The problem of the low quality of some Islamic educational institutions is indicated by the fact that among the stakeholders there are those who have not been able to prepare strategic plans, there are those who are capable but not yet serious and even still consider it a mere formality, there are those who are full of awareness but there are also those who join in. In fact, if strategic planning can be made and implemented correctly and supported by leadership commitment, then strategic planning can provide benefits for Islamic educational institutions, including: (1) Strategic planning can strengthen the "critical mass" into a cohesive team, because it is directed to adhere to core values, main systems and common goals, (2) Strategic planning can help to optimize the performance of Islamic educational institutions, (3) Strategic planning can help leaders to always focus attention and adhere to a framework for continuous improvement efforts, (4) Strategic planning provides guidelines for daily decision making, and (5) Strategic planning always makes it easy to measure the organization's progress in achieving its goals of improving quality and productivity. Awareness of the benefits of educational strategic planning is something that needs to be considered to create quality Islamic education.

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